

Design and Deployment of Event-based File Processing in a Gateway

Rajesh Kalyanam, Rob Campbell, Jungha Woo, Nicole Brewer, Lan Zhao, and Carol Song

Research Computing
Purdue University
West Lafayette, USA

ABSTRACT

We describe our experience in designing and deploying a scalable and extensible approach to processing files in response to create, update, rename, and delete operations on a science gateway. The MyGeoHub gateway [1] is based on the HUBzero framework [2] and extends it with novel capabilities that enable researchers to self-manage, visualize, search, and discover geospatial data from various domains. Specifically, structured geospatial metadata is extracted automatically and ingested into HUBzero's search infrastructure, and embedded web preview of geospatial files is enabled by processing and registering geospatial files to a map server. Since HUBzero (and MyGeoHub) enables both the web content management system (CMS) and containerized tools (running on a separate server) to expose a shared file space, any such file processing needs to be agnostic to the source of the file events.

We utilize a combination of kernel-level event monitoring (via auditd), event message filtering via Logstash, and a Kubernetes/Helm-based cloud deployment of a high-availability message broker (RabbitMQ), scalable, extensible message processing worker containers, and a QGIS map server to implement our file processing pipeline. The various features of our technology choices that were leveraged and the lessons learned during this deployment are as follows: (1) the ability to filter, simplify, and/or augment the kernel messages via Logstash enables us to reduce the load on the message broker; (2) the ability to expose the message broker and map server via static fully qualified domain names (FQDN) through the use of the Kubernetes Ingress Load Balancer (ILB) reduces the need for configuration updates on the gateway; (3) the ability to deploy rolling updates to the message processing workers via Helm upgrades enables a phased deployment and evaluation of feature extensions; and (4) the use of QGIS projects to manage map layers for files in a particular folder speeds up preview

processing and simplifies the web preview interface implementation.

Our file processing pipeline is designed to be independent of the MyGeoHub gateway and can be easily integrated with any other gateway platform as long as file event messages in appropriate formats are generated and streamed to the message broker. The file processing pipeline is currently deployed to Jetstream cloud [3] and the corresponding Helm charts can be found in our GitHub repository [4].

Keywords—gateways; pipeline; file processing; Kubernetes; message queue

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We would like to thank the HUBzero team for their assistance in configuring and integrating the file processing pipeline with the MyGeoHub gateway. We would also like to thank the Jetstream team for their cloud computing resources and support. This work is sponsored by NSF award #1835822.

REFERENCES

- [1] Kalyanam, R., Zhao, L., Song, C., Biehl, L., Kearney, D., Kim, I.L., Shin, J., Villoria, N. and Merwade, V., 2019. MyGeoHub—A sustainable and evolving geospatial science gateway. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 94, pp.820-832.
- [2] McLennan, M. and Kennell, R., 2010. HUBzero: a platform for dissemination and collaboration in computational science and engineering. *Computing in Science & Engineering*, 12(2), pp.48-53.
- [3] Stewart, C.A., Cockerill, T.M., Foster, I., Hancock, D., Merchant, N., Skidmore, E., Stanzione, D., Taylor, J., Tuecke, S., Turner, G. and Vaughn, M., 2015, July. Jetstream: a self-provisioned, scalable science and engineering cloud environment. In *Proceedings of the 2015 XSEDE Conference: Scientific Advancements Enabled by Enhanced Cyberinfrastructure* (pp. 1-8).
- [4] <https://github.com/geoedf/idata-pipeline>